

SYNTHESIS OF QUINAZOLINES (AND BENZOGLYOXALINES). PART V.

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Certain quinazolines and benzoimidazoles have been synthesised with an alkyl-amino side-chain. In the benzoimidazole series a basic tertiary nitrogen situated at the β -carbon atom in the chain loses the nitrogen complex in the form of the corresponding secondary base and the conjugated unsaturated product, thus produced, undergoes polymerisation. 3 :4-Methylenedioxy-6-aminoacetylbenzylamine is remarkably stable and does not undergo ring-closure.

A description is included of a substance which can be called as methylenedioxy-*isovasicone*.

In the present investigation, an attempt has been made to synthesise quinazolines related to vasicine and glyoxalines with an aminoalkyl side-chain so that the physiological action of these compounds can be fully investigated. β -Substituted phenylethylamines have well marked sympathomimetic action. Chatterji (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2965) has prepared β -benzimidazoleethylamine which, however, failed to show any pressor action even in relatively large dose. For the purpose of the synthesis of the benzimidazoles, *o*-nitroaniline has been condensed with chloroacetyl and β -chloropropionyl chloride to give (I). The substances of the type (I) were then condensed with piperidine or diethylamine to give (II)₂. The amine related to (II) cyclised

(I)

(II)

(III)

to the corresponding glyoxaline (III) on being heated with sodium acetate and acetic acid. In the case where $n=2$, the amine related to (II) was smoothly produced but under all conditions of cyclisation the aminoalkyl side-chain or piperidine residue was extruded resulting in the production of a polymer of the substance (IV)

(IV)

(V)

For the synthesis of the quinazolins, *o*-aminobenzamide was condensed with chloroacetyl and β -chloropropionyl chloride and the products (V) were condensed with diethylamine or piperidine to (VI).

(VI)

(VII)

The substances of the type of (VI) in alcoholic solution easily cyclised to (VII) with a drop of potassium hydroxide solution at 50-60°. This general method of the formation of quinazolins has its limitations in that the acetyl derivative of 3:4-methylenedioxy-6-nitrobenzylamine (VIII) when reduced to (IX) did not pass into the corresponding quinazoline under all the conditions tried. The substance (IX) showed remarkable stability, whilst the analogous substance (X) presented no difficulty in its conversion to (XI).

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

We can offer no explanation at this stage for the remarkable stability of (IX), but it is of so unusual a nature that we wish to draw attention to this peculiar behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Nitro- ω -piperidinoacetanilide (II, $n=1$, NR₂ replaced by piperidino).—A mixture of *o*-nitrochloroacetanilide (3 g), piperidine (3 c.c.) and benzene (20 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath for 2 hours. The precipitated piperidine hydrochloride was filtered, the benzene solution washed with water and then the solvent removed. The pale yellow residue crystallised from hot petroleum ether in light yellow needles with slight greenish tinge, m.p. 85°. (Found: N, 15.97. C₁₃H₁₇O₃N₃ requires N, 15.79 per cent).

o-Amino- ω -piperidinoacetanilide.—The foregoing nitro compound (2 g.) dissolved in alcohol (12 c.c.) was mixed with dilute hydrochloric acid (25 c.c. of 15%) so that no precipitation occurred. The mixture cooled to 0°, was reduced with zinc dust (15 g.) with small quantities at a time. The filtered solution was basified with ammonia in presence of ammonium chloride and the colourless oil extracted with chloroform. whence it was redissolved with dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated with ammonia. After second precipitation, the oil solidified when cooled and scratched, yield 1.5 g. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 173° and gave a strong diazo reaction. (Found: C, 67.04; H, 8.28; N, 18.04. C₁₃H₁₉ON₃ requires C, 66.96; H, 8.16; N, 18.02 per cent).

Piperidinomethylbenzimidazole (III, $n=1$, NR₂=piperidino).—A mixture of the foregoing amine (0.5 g.) fused sodium acetate (1 g.), acetic acid (8 c.c.) was refluxed for an hour. After dilution with water, the mixture was basified with ammonia when a colourless crystalline substance separated. It was crystallised from dry benzene in shining plates, m.p. 201°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: N, 19.52. C₁₃H₁₇N₃ requires N, 19.53 per cent). The urate of this base has a solubility of 0.105% in water at 20°.

o-Nitro- ω -diethylaminoacetanilide (II, $n=1$, R = Et).—A mixture of *o*-nitrochloroacetanilide (3 g.), diethylamine (3 c.c.) and benzene (30 c.c.) was refluxed for 2 hours. The product, isolated as described before, crystallised from alcohol in yellowish needles, m.p. 70° (Found: N, 16.83; C₁₃H₁₇O₃N₃ requires N, 16.74 per cent).

o-Amino- ω -diethylaminoacetanilide.—The nitro compound (2 g.) dissolved in alcohol (25 c.c.) was added to a solution of ferrous sulphate (15 g.) in water (40 c.c.), basified with ammonia and kept at 80°. The

mixture was heated on the steam-bath for 20 minutes and then filtered hot. The filtrate was extracted with chloroform and the chloroform layer washed with dilute acid. A dark coloured impurity remained in the chloroform layer. The base was regenerated from the aqueous solution and was then taken up in ether. The dried ether solution furnished the amine on removal of the solvent. The substance was crystallised from hot petroleum ether in shining plates, m.p. 81°. (Found: N, 19'32. $C_{12}H_{19}ON^w$ requires N, 19'0 per cent).

α-Diethylaminomethylbenzimidazole (III, $n = 1$, R = Et).—The cyclisation was effected as described before. The base was crystallised from a hot mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (1:1 in pale yellow plates, m.p. 169°. (Found: N, 20'96. $C_{12}H_{16}N_3$ requires N, 20'60 per cent). The substance showed no tests for a free amino group whilst the amine, m.p. 81°, gave a brilliant scarlet azo-dye. The urate of the substance, m.p. 169°, had 0'42% solubility in water at 26°.

o-Nitro-β-chloropropionanilide prepared in the usual way from *o*-nitroaniline and *β*-chloropropionyl chloride, had m.p. 85° after crystallisation from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 12'45. $C_9H_9O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 12'25 per cent).

o-Nitro-β-piperidinopropionanilide was prepared in the same manner as the corresponding acetanilide. The substance crystallised from hot petroleum ether in long greenish yellow needles, m.p. 44°. (Found: N, 15'0. $C_{14}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires N, 15'16 per cent).

o-Amino-β-piperidinopropionanilide.—The above nitro compound (2 g.) in alcohol (15 c.c.) was reduced with zinc dust (15 g.) and hydrochloric acid (25 c.c. of 15%). The base was isolated in the manner previously described.

The colourless crystalline material isolated from the chloroform extract was recrystallised from boiling ligroin in fine needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 68'0; H, 8'59; N, 16'84. $C_{14}H_{21}ON_3$ requires C, 68'0; H, 8'50; N, 17'0 per cent). The substance gave the test for an amino group.

The polymer of the Substance (IV).—The foregoing amine (1 g.), fused sodium acetate (4 g.) and acetic acid (25 c.c.) were refluxed for 1 hour. Thereafter, the mixture was diluted with cold water and basified with ammonia, when a colourless flocculent precipitate formed. This substance crystallised from alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 290° (decomp.), yield 0'5 g. [Found: C, 74'96; H, 4'87; N, 19'50. $(C_9H_8N_2)_n$ requires C, 75'0; H, 5'55; N, 19'46 per cent]. It is evident that the piperidine part has been knocked off during ring-closure resulting in an ethylene derivative. The high melting point points to the substance being a polymer. The substance

gave tests for unsaturation. Heating with zinc chloride, phosphoryl chloride or merely heating the amino compound at 200° results in the elimination of the piperidine residue with simultaneous ring-closure.

o-Nitro- β -diethylaminopropionanilide (II, $n = 2$, R = Et) prepared in the usual way was an oil which decomposed on distillation.

The related amine was prepared by reduction as follows:—A solution of stannous chloride dihydrate (7 g.) in acetic anhydride (7 c.c.) was diluted to 30 c.c. with glacial acetic acid. The solution was then saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0° . The foregoing nitro compound (2 g.) was added, with stirring to 60 c.c. of the ice-cold reagent prepared as above. After an hour, the separated tin double compound was filtered and then dissolved in a small quantity of water. The solution was basified with potassium hydroxide solution in the cold and the liberated base extracted with chloroform. The dried chloroform solution furnished the base on evaporation. It crystallised from hot petroleum ether in colourless needles, m.p. 56° . (Found: C, 66.56; H, 9.44. $C_{13}H_{21}ON_2$ requires C, 66.38; H, 8.94 per cent). This amine, on being heated with sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished the same substance as was obtained in the case of the corresponding piperidino compound. In this case diethylamine was extruded from the chain during ring-closure. The identity of this product with the polymer of (IV) described before was established by mixed m.p. and full elementary analysis. The identity of the products in the case of the *o*-amino- β -piperidino and the *o*-amino- β -diethylaminopropionanilide establishes fully the view that the basic part in either case is extruded during ring-closure.

The Quinazoline Series: o-w-Chloroacetylaminobenzamide.—*o*-Aminobenzamide (2 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) and pyridine (4 c.c.) was treated with chloroacetyl chloride (2 c.c.). The sticky brown solids were washed with water, dried, and crystallised from a large volume of benzene in light brown needles, m.p. 171° . (Found: N, 13.14. $C_9H_9O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 13.18 per cent).

o-a-Piperidinoacetylaminobenzamide (VI, $n = 1$, $R_2 =$ piperidino).—The above chloro compound (2 g.), piperidine (4 c.c.) in benzene (40 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours. After the removal of precipitated piperidine hydrochloride, the benzene solution furnished a dark product which was crystallised twice from hot benzene (charcoal) in light brown needles, m.p. 186° (decomp.), yield 1 g. (Found: N, 15.90. $C_{14}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.09 per cent).

2-Piperidinomethyl-4-oxyquinazoline (VII, $n = 1$, $R_2 =$ piperidino).—A drop of potassium hydroxide solution was added to a solution of the

substance (0.5 g.) described in the preceding section in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) and the mixture heated at 50-60° for 1 hour. After dilution with water (25 c.c.), the base was extracted with chloroform, the solution dried, and then the solvent removed. The residue crystallised from hot benzene—petroleum ether mixture (3:2) in fine colourless needles, m.p. 170°; yield 0.4 g. (Found: N, 17.54. $C_{14}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 17.28 per cent).

2- α -Diethylaminomethyl-4-oxyquinazoline (VII, $n=1$, R = Et).—*o*- α -Diethylaminoacetylaminobenzamide was prepared as the corresponding piperidino compound with diethylamine. It was crystallised from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) in light yellowish needles, m.p. 165° (decomp.). After ring-closure with alkali, as described before, the substance crystallised from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (1:1), m.p. 85° (Found: N, 17.85; $C_{13}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 18.18 per cent).

o- β -Piperidinopropionylaminobenzamide was prepared by interacting *o*- β -chloropropionylaminobenzamide and piperidine in the usual manner. The substance crystallises from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 140° (Found: N, 15.41 $C_{15}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.27 per cent).

2- β -Piperidinoethyl-4-oxyquinazoline was prepared by the action of a drop of alkali on the alcoholic solution of the foregoing substance at 50-60°. It crystallised from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether in colourless needles, m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 16.47. $C_{15}H_{19}ON_3$ requires N, 16.34 per cent).

o- β -Diethylaminopropionylaminobenzamide (VI, $n=2$, R = Et) had m.p. 99° after crystallisation from petroleum ether. (Found: N, 15.7. $C_{14}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.97 per cent).

2- β -Diethylaminoethyl-4-oxyquinazoline (VII, $n=2$, R = Et) was prepared by the ring-closure of the above substance with alkali in the manner described before. The product crystallised from a mixture of petroleum ether (60%) and benzene (40%) in long needles, m.p. 122°. (Found: N, 17.10. $C_{14}H_{19}ON_3$ requires N, 17.14 per cent).

Piperonyl Alcohol. — 3 : 4 - Methyleneedioxyphenylmethyl alcohol has been obtained in 90% yield by the electrolytic reduction of piperonal by Shima (*Mem. Coll., Sci. Kyoto*, 1928, (A), 11, 407) but the following method is much easier to work and gives equally good yield.

Formalin (135 c.c.) was added to a solution of piperonal (100 g.) in methanol (120 c.c.) and the solution warmed to 60°. Sodium hydroxide (90 g.) dissolved in minimum amount of water was slowly added with constant shaking during 1/2 hour. The solution became dark during the addition of the alkali. After refluxing on the steam-bath for 1/2 hour

methanol was distilled off and the mixture diluted with water (300 c.c.) and then extracted with ether (400 c.c.). The ethereal solution was dried and the solvent removed. The residue was distilled *in vacuo* and the distillate of piperonyl alcohol solidified to a colourless substance, m.p. 56°; yield 0.0 g.

3:4-Methylenedioxy-6-nitrobenzyl chloride was prepared by the excellent method of Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1758). We observed that after two-thirds of the nitric acid had been added, a sudden rise of temperature of the reaction mixture takes place. We found, however, that the initial addition of sulphuric acid to the reaction mixture after saturation with hydrogen chloride and before the addition of nitric acid, prevents this sudden reaction and the product crystallises quite easily in stout prisms from methanol, m.p. 86°.

In an experiment when piperonyl alcohol (90 g.) in acetic acid (100 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride was nitrated with nitric acid (170 c.c., *d* 1.42) and sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) at 5-10°, 65 g. of the crystallised product were obtained.

N-3:4-Methylenedioxy-6-nitrobenzylphthalimide.—6-Nitrohomopiperonyl chloride (5 g.), potassium phthalimide (4.25 g.), potassium iodide (1 g.) were mixed together and heated on the steam-bath for 20 minutes with absolute alcohol (15 c.c.). After cooling the precipitated solids were collected and well washed with water and then crystallised from hot acetic acid. It crystallised in pale yellow needles, m.p. 218°, yield 8 g. (Found: N, 8.58. $C_{16}H_{10}O_6N_2$ requires N, 8.5 per cent.)

3:4-Methylenedioxy-6-nitrobenzylamine (VIII).—The foregoing compound (5 g.) suspended in alcohol (50 c.c.) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (*cf.* Ing and Manske, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2348). The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours, when a thick gelatinous precipitate separated. At this stage, hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.16; 25 c.c.) was introduced and the heating continued for another 2 hours. The precipitate phthalyl hydrazide was filtered off, the filtrate evaporated to dryness on the steam-bath. The residue was lixiviated with water and filtered from a sticky insoluble solid. The aqueous solution on concentration gave the hydrochloride of 3:4-methylenedioxy-6-nitrobenzylamine which was recrystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 196° (decomp.), yield 2.9 g. (Found: N, 14.46. $C_9H_9O_4N_2 \cdot HCl$ requires N, 14.28 per cent.)

The free base liberated with alkali was extracted with chloroform, whence a yellow solid was obtained. It crystallised from benzene in fine needles, m.p. 105° (decomp.). (Found: N, 13.75. $C_9H_9O_4N_2$ requires N, 14.28 per cent.). The base is moderately soluble in water,

alcohol, benzene and ethyl acetate. It is slowly oxidised when kept exposed to air.

3:4-Methylenedioxy-6-nitroacetylbenzylamine was prepared in the usual manner. After crystallisation from alcohol (pale brown needles) it had m.p. 204° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.76. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.87 per cent.).

3:4-Methylenedioxy-6-aminoacetylbenzylamine (IX) was prepared by reducing the foregoing nitro compound (1 g.) with the stannous chloride reagent (30 c.c.) described before. The tin double compound, dissolved in the least quantity of water was basified with potassium hydroxide solution. The base was extracted with chloroform, whence it came out as a semi-solid mass. After repeated crystallisation from benzene, it came out in fine colourless needles, m.p. 126° (decomp.), yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 57.60; H, 6.01; N, 13.69. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires C, 57.69; H, 5.76; N, 13.46 per cent.). The substance gave tests for an amine and resisted ring-closure with (a) sodium acetate and acetic acid, (b) acetic anhydride, (c) alkali in alcoholic solution and (d) phosphoryl chloride.

N-3:4-Methylenedioxy-6-nitrobenzylsuccinimide (X) —A mixture of 6-nitropiperonyl chloride (5 g.), potassium succinimide (3.2 g.), absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 3 hours. The separated solids were collected after cooling and after washing with water were crystallised from hot alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 175°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 10.27. $C_{12}H_{10}O_6N_2$ requires N, 10.07 per cent.).

Methylenedioxyisovasicone (XI).—A solution of stannous chloride (5 g.) in hydrochloric acid (d 1.16, 5 c.c.) was warmed to 50° and small portions of the foregoing nitro compound (1 g.) added with stirring. After the addition of the whole amount, the temperature was raised to 60-70° for ½ hour. The mixture was then diluted with water and strongly basified with potassium hydroxide solution in the cold. The liberated base was extracted with ethyl acetate, solvent removed, and then crystallised from hot alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 267°. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 4.5; N, 12.1. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.3; N, 12.2 per cent.).

All the analyses recorded above were done by the micro method.